

Reaction to submergence of parents and F₁ and F₂ populations of crosses.

Cross	Submergence survival (%)			v ²	Ratio	Probability
	Parents	F ₁	F ₂			
BKNFR76106-13-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	84.3 0.0	72	54	0.21	9:7	0.50-0.70
BKNFR76106-16-0-1/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	80.5 0.0	19	51	1.12	9:7	0.25-0.30
IR8234-0T-9-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	73.4 0.0	65	41	9.45	7:9	0.01-0.001
IR21567-16-2-2/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	76.0 0.0	32	35	3.50	7:9	0.05-0.10
IR29012-4-1-3/ IR11288-B-B-69-1	81.3 0.0	72	43	0.02	7:9	0.70-0.90
IR31406-333-1 IR11288-B-B-69-1	10.0 0.0	72	59	0.31	9:7	0.50-0.70

Two types of segregation ratios were observed in the F₂: 9:7 for crosses where tolerant parents derived tolerant genes from FR13A and Kurkaruppan, and 7:9 for crosses where tolerant parents derived

tolerant genes from moderately tolerant KLG986 and Nam Sagui 19. These ratios can be explained by the complementary action of at least two genes. ■

Stress tolerance – adverse soils

Genetic variability in rice genotypes planted in sodic soil

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We evaluated the genetic variability and heritability of desirable traits in 56 rice

genotypes sown Jul 1989 in sodic soil (pH 8.9).

Planting was done in 5-m rows with three 35-d-old seedlings/hill at 25- × 25-cm spacing. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications. Maximum and minimum temperatures during crop duration were 32.7-27.4 and 26.4-14.9 °C.

All traits except flag leaf thickness showed a wide range of phenotypic

Range, mean, coefficients of variability, heritability, and genetic advance of 16 traits in 56 rice genotypes grown in sodic soils. Faizabad, India, 1989.

Trait	Range	Grand mean and SE	PCV	GCV	ECV	Heritability (%)	Genetic advance in % of mean	
Plant height (cm)	67.9-145.0	90.4 p	3.2	15.9	15.3	4.3	92.7	30.4
Tillers per plant	3.4- 8.7	6.0 p	0.6	21.3	17.4	12.3	67.1	29.4
Flag leaf thickness (mm)	0.6- 1.3	0.9 p	0.02	16.7	16.3	2.0	95.7	33.0
Flag leaf area (cm ²)	18.3- 56.5	34.0 p	1.5	23.1	22.5	5.5	94.4	45.0
Days to panicle emergence	77.7-122.3	101.0 p	1.6	8.8	8.6	2.0	94.9	17.2
Days to 50% flowering	82.0-131.0	104.8 p	1.2	8.3	8.2	1.4	97.2	16.6
Days to maturity	103.0-155.0	136.8 p	1.8	9.8	9.7	1.6	97.5	19.8
Panicles per plant	2.8- 6.8	4.9 p	0.6	24.1	19.3	14.3	64.3	31.8
Panicle length (cm)	18.4- 28.1	23.5 p	0.9	9.0	7.8	4.6	74.1	13.8
Spikelets per panicle	61.7-270.7	137.2 p	13.9	33.0	30.5	14.4	85.9	58.4
Filled grains per panicle	52.0-239.3	117.4 p	14.4	32.9	29.3	15.1	79.1	53.6
Grain sterility (%)	5.0- 41.0	14.0 p	2.7	55.4	50.3	23.2	82.5	94.7
Biological yield per plant (g)	12.7- 45.3	25.8 p	3.4	33.4	29.2	16.2	76.4	52.3
Grain yield per plant (g)	6.8- 21.6	11.4 p	1.6	27.6	24.0	13.6	41.3	26.6
Harvest index (%)	29.7- 62.0	45.9 p	4.8	20.9	16.4	12.9	61.8	43.0
100-grain wt (g)	1.6- 3.3	2.6 p	0.1	13.9	13.5	3.1	92.3	23.3

variation (see table). The phenotypic coefficient of variation (PCV) was higher than the genotypic coefficient of variation (GCV) for all traits. PCV ranged from 8.3 for days to 50% flowering to 55.4 for grain sterility.

Tillers/plant, flag leaf area, paniced plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index had high values for both GCV and PCV.

Tillers/plant, panicles/plant, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, grain sterility, biological yield/plant, grain yield/plant, and harvest index showed higher environmental coefficient of variability (ECV). This indicates that these traits were more susceptible to environmental and agro-ecotypic factors, especially to soil sodicity and temperature variations.

Grain sterility showed higher PCV, GCV, ECV, and genetic advance (in % of mean) than other traits, indicating this trait could be used in breeding for salt tolerance. Heritability was high for all traits except grain yield/plant.

Grain sterility, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, biological yield/plant, flag leaf area, and harvest index showed higher values for genetic advance.

Panicles/plant, flag leaf area, spikelets/panicle, filled grains/panicle, sterility, and yield may be good selection criteria for screening rice genotypes for sodic soil conditions. ■

Absorption of nutrients and their replaceable functions in rice varieties tolerant of and sensitive to K deficiency

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The experiment was conducted with two varieties: Xiang-Zao-Nuo 1 (XZN 1) is tolerant of K deficiency, Shuang-Gui 36 (SG36) is sensitive. Seedlings at the three-leaf stage were grown on complete and K-deficient nutrient solutions. Dry weight of seedlings was determined 34, 38, and 41 d after planting. Content of Cu, Mn, Zn, Fe, Mg, K, Na, and Ca in dried shoots was analyzed.

Seedling dry weight indicated that XZN 1 was not affected by K-deficient